

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND ELASTIC LIMITS OF HYBRID LAMINATES

James N. Craddock

Department of Civil Engineering and Mechanics
Southern Illinois University
Carbondale, Illinois 62901
USA

Summary

Laminates of two or more materials are often used in an effort to optimize some aspects of the performance of the resulting hybrid. This paper is an analytical study of the effect of hybridization on the mechanical behavior of hybrid laminates. The properties examined in this work were the effective engineering constants E_x , E_y , G_{xy} , and ν_{xy} . The strength of hybrid laminates under inplane biaxial loading is also considered. Additionally, the bending response of hybrids is studied by looking at the equivalent bending stiffness, EI , and the maximum bending moment, M_x . Material combinations used included fiberglass and graphite-epoxies and Kevlar and graphite-epoxies. Four representative layups were used in this study. These were uniaxial, cross-ply, angle-ply, and quasi-isotropic layups. The results are most interesting for the glass-graphite hybrids where the lamina thicknesses differ. This leads to bending results where the first-ply-failure can occur at inner layers first; and adding stiffer layers, ply-for-ply, can reduce the bending stiffness. The results presented herein provide general trends of the mechanical properties and of the strength of hybrid laminates and should provide qualitative information for design.

Introduction

Hybrid composite laminates are made with layers of different materials. The use of two or more materials in a single laminate allows a designer to optimize certain performance characteristics of a structure. As an example, a hybrid combination of Kevlar and graphite will exhibit better impact resistance than an all graphite laminate while retaining some of the higher stiffness and strength of the graphite laminates. Hybrids are often combinations of graphite/epoxy with either Kevlar/epoxy or fiberglass/epoxy.

This paper examines the effect of hybridization on the mechanical behavior of laminates. Material properties studied include the effective engineering constants, the moduli E_x , E_y , G_{xy} and the Poisson's ratio ν_{xy} . Failure envelopes for biaxial inplane loadings are obtained based on the quadratic interaction failure criterion (also known as the Tsai-Wu criterion). The bending response of hybrids was also examined by studying the equivalent bending stiffness, EI , and the maximum bending moment, M_x .

The layups used were a uniaxial layup, (0_2^0) ; a cross-ply layup, $(0_{10}^0/90_{10}^0)_s$; an angle-ply geometry, $(0_{10}^0/+30_{10}^0)_s$; and a quasi-isotropic laminate, $(0_{10}^0/+45_{10}^0/90_{10}^0)_s$. These configurations were selected to be a representative cross-section of the types of geometries used in practice. For all four layups, four material combinations were used. These were graphite-epoxy as the base material with either Kevlar or fiberglass as the second material, and Kevlar and fiberglass as the base material with graphite-epoxy as the second or hybridizing material.

Analytical Procedure

The first step in finding the effective laminate engineering constants (1) is the determination of the inplane stiffness matrix, $[A]$, from classical lamination theory (2). For a balanced, symmetric laminate

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_x &= N_x/h = (1/h)(A_{11}\epsilon_x + A_{12}\epsilon_y) \\ \sigma_y &= N_y/h = (1/h)(A_{12}\epsilon_x + A_{22}\epsilon_y) \\ \sigma_{xy} &= N_{xy}/h = (1/h)(A_{66}\gamma_{xy})\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

where N_x , N_y , and N_{xy} are the stress resultants and h is the total laminate thickness. The stress-strain relationships for the laminate can be written in terms of the effective engineering properties as

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_x &= (1/E_x)(\sigma_x - \nu_{xy}\sigma_y) \\ \epsilon_y &= (1/E_y)(\sigma_y - \nu_{yx}\sigma_x) \\ \gamma_{xy} &= \sigma_{xy}/G_{xy}\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

where E_x and E_y are the effective Young's moduli in the x and y directions, G_{xy} is the effective shear modulus, and ν_{xy} and ν_{yx} are the effective Poisson's ratios. By inverting equation (1) and matching terms with equation (2) the following relationships are obtained

$$\begin{aligned}E_x &= \frac{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}{hA_{22}} & G_{xy} &= A_{66}/h \\ E_y &= \frac{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}{hA_{11}} & \nu_{xy} &= A_{12}/A_{22} \\ & & \nu_{yx} &= A_{12}/A_{11}\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

As previously stated these results are valid only for balanced, symmetric laminates. All laminates considered in this work are of this type.

There have been many failure criteria proposed for composite laminates (3). The one selected for use in this work is the quadratic interaction failure criterion as proposed by Tsai and Wu (4). This criterion may be expressed as

$$F_1\sigma_1 + F_2\sigma_2 + F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_{66}\sigma_6^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 = 1 \quad (4)$$

The strength parameters, F_{ij} , are found from unidirectional strengths in tension and compression. These results can be expressed by

$$F_1 = \frac{1}{X^T} - \frac{1}{X^C}$$

$$F_2 = \frac{1}{Y^T} - \frac{1}{Y^C}$$

$$F_{66} = \frac{1}{S^2}$$

$$F_{11} = \frac{1}{X^T X^C}$$

$$F_{22} = \frac{1}{Y^T Y^C} \quad (5)$$

where X^T and X^C are the strengths in the fiber direction in tension and compression, Y^T and Y^C are the strengths in the transverse direction, and S is the shear strength. The interaction parameter F_{12} can either be measured or else calculated as (5)

$$F_{12} = -\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{F_{11}F_{22}} \quad (6)$$

This criterion is applied ply-by-ply and requires that the stresses be expressed in the intrinsic coordinate system where σ_1 is the stress in the fiber direction, σ_2 is the stress perpendicular to the fibers and σ_6 is the shear stress in the 1-2 system. Failure for the laminate, in this work, was considered to be the point of first-ply-failure.

The effective bending stiffness can be approximated from the bending stiffness matrix $[D]$. If unit width is assumed and M_x is the only non-zero moment resultant then

$$\begin{aligned} M_x &= D_{11}^k x + D_{12}^k y + D_{16}^k xy \\ 0 &= D_{12}^k x + D_{12}^k y + D_{26}^k xy \\ 0 &= D_{16}^k x + D_{26}^k y + D_{66}^k xy \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

If the above equation is inverted then

$$d_{11} M_x = {}^k x \quad (8)$$

where $[d] = [D]^{-1}$. If equation (8) is compared to results from strength of materials

$$\frac{M_x}{EI} = y'' = {}^k x \quad (9)$$

it is readily seen that

$$1/d_{11} = EI \quad (10)$$

Results

Material Properties

Four laminates were considered, a uniaxial (0_{20}^0) laminate, a cross-ply ($0_{10}^0/90_{10}^0$)_S, an angle-ply ($0_{10}^0/(+30)_5$)_S and a quasi-isotropic ($0_{10}^0/(+45)_5/90_{10}^0$)_S laminate. Four material systems were used. These were fiberglass-epoxy with 0^0 layers replaced by graphite-epoxy; Kevlar-epoxy with 0^0 layers replaced by graphite; and graphite-epoxy with 0^0 layer replaced by glass and by graphite. The material properties for each of these three materials are given in Table I.

Table I. Material Properties (5)

<u>Property</u>	<u>Graphite/Epoxy</u>	<u>Kevlar/Epoxy</u>	<u>Glass/Epoxy</u>
E_1 (psi)	2.625×10^7	1.102×10^7	5.600×10^6
E_2 (psi)	1.494×10^6	7.977×10^5	$1,200 \times 10^6$
G (psi)	1.040×10^6	3.336×10^5	6.005×10^5
ν_{12}	0.28	0.34	0.26
thickness (in)	.005	.005	.010

The strengths for these materials are given in Table II.

Table II. Strength Data (5)

<u>Strength</u>	<u>Graphite/Epoxy</u>	<u>Kevlar/Epoxy</u>	<u>Glass/Epoxy</u>
X^T (ksi)	217.50	203.10	154.0
X^C (ksi)	217.50	34.10	88.5
Y^T (ksi)	5.81	1.74	4.5
Y^C (ksi)	356.80	7.69	17.1
S (ksi)	9.86	4.93	10.4

Effective Engineering Constants

The effective engineering constants depend only on the number of layers of each material and not on the stacking sequence. The sequence is important in determining bending results. In this work, the properties of the original laminate were calculated. The 0^0 layers were then replaced from the outer layer inward by the second material. Results for each property are plotted as a percent of the property in the original laminate.

In Figure 1 results are presented for a uniaxial graphite laminate with Kevlar replacing the graphite. It can be seen that the moduli decrease linearly while the Poisson's ratio increases. In Figure 2 results are presented for the same uniaxial graphite laminate with glass as the second material. In this case the results are non-linear for each property. The Poisson's ratio is very nearly linear since the values of the Poisson's ratio for graphite/epoxy and fiberglass/epoxy are very close (.28 and .26 respectively). The non-linearity in the other properties is a result of the different thicknesses of graphite and glass. In the previous case Kevlar and graphite have the same thicknesses.

Figure 1. Material Property Variations for a Uniaxial Graphite-Kevlar Hybrid.

In Figures 3 and 4 results are presented for a cross-ply $(0^\circ_{10}/90^\circ_{10})_s$ laminate. The material in Figure 3 is Kevlar with graphite replacing the 0° layers, and in Figure 4 it is glass and graphite. These results show the same pattern as the previous figures, that being the linear variation of the effective moduli for the Kevlar-graphite laminate and the non-linear results for the glass-graphite hybrid. The glass-graphite results are more nearly linear than in the uniaxial case. This can be attributed to the core of 90° layers which remain unchanged. Similar results were found for the other layups.

Figure 2. Material Property Variations for a Uniaxial Graphite-Glass Hybrid.

Figure 3. Material Property Variations for a Cross-Ply Kevlar-Graphite Hybrid.

Figure 4. Material Property Variations for a Cross-Ply Glass-Graphite Hybrid.

Elastic Limits

Failure envelopes are presented in Figures 5 and 6. The results for a quasi-isotropic $(0_{10}^0/+45_5^0/90_{10}^0)_s$ laminate of graphite with Kevlar are presented in Figure 5. In Figure 6, results are shown for an angle-ply $(0_{10}^0/+30_5^0)_s$ laminate of graphite combined with glass. Both of these plots show how the introduction of the second, less strong, material (Kevlar or glass) can dramatically reduce the size of the resulting envelope. In Figures 7 and 8 results are presented for angle-ply $(0_{10}^0/+30_5^0)_s$ laminates of glass and Kevlar respectively, both combined with some 0^0 graphite fibers. These show that adding a stronger layer does less to increase strength than adding a weaker layer does to reduce the overall strength.

Bending Results

The equivalent bending stiffness and maximum bending moment as functions of the number of Kevlar 0^0 layers in a graphite quasi-isotropic $(0_{10}^0/+45_5^0/90_{10}^0)_s$ laminate are shown in Figure 9. It can be seen that the equivalent stiffness, EI, decreases almost linearly while the maximum moment drops markedly when the first Kevlar layer is introduced. First-ply-failure in this case occurs at the outermost compression layer. The relatively low compressive strength, X^C , of Kevlar accounts for this drop. The behavior of an angle-ply $(0_{10}^0/+30_5^0)_s$ combination of graphite and glass is shown in Figure 10. It can be observed that the stiffness decreases to a minimum at about 6 layers of glass at 0^0 and then increases. This is explained again

Figure 5. Failure Envelopes for a Quasi-Isotropic Graphite-Kevlar Hybrid with 0, 50, and 100% of 0° Layers of Kevlar.

Figure 6. Failure Envelopes for an Angle-Ply Graphite-Glass Hybrid with 0, 50, and 100% of 0° Layers of Glass.

Figure 7. Failure Envelopes for an Angle-Ply Glass-Graphite Hybrid with 0, 50, and 100% 0° Layers of Graphite.

Figure 8. Failure Envelopes for an Angle-Ply Kevlar-Graphite Hybrid with 0, 50, and 100% of 0° Layers of Graphite.

Figure 9. Bending Results for a Quasi-Isotropic Graphite-Kevlar Hybrid.

Figure 10. Bending Results for an Angle-Ply Graphite-Glass Hybrid.

by the greater thickness of the glass contributing to a larger moment of inertia I . The maximum bending moment behavior is even less intuitively obvious. In this case it appears that adding the weaker glass layers can actually increase the maximum moment. This fact can be explained by examining the stress and strain distributions through the thickness of the laminate. The strain varies linearly as it must for continuity. The low value of the modulus E_1 for glass compared to graphite give lower stresses in the glass layers. This coupled with the strength in compression of glass being about 40% of that for graphite leads to the outermost graphite fiber failing first before the glass fibers. This leads to the increase and eventually discontinuity in the maximum moment curve. After the discontinuity the outermost glass fiber fails first. The maximum moment again increases when the bending stiffness starts to increase. The results for a quasi-isotropic $(0^\circ_{10}/+45^\circ_5/90^\circ_{10})_S$ laminate made of glass combined with graphite are shown in Figure 11. Here it is seen that the replacement of the outer 0° layers of glass by graphite decreases the maximum moment. This is again due to the graphite carrying a higher stress. In the all glass laminate, the outer 45° layers on the compression side fail first. As soon as the graphite is introduced, it carries so much stress, due to its high modulus, that the outer 0° layer fails first. All of the inner layers carry less load and the maximum moment actually decreases at first. After the initial drop M_{MAX} increases with the addition of more graphite layers. In this case EI is increasing as the higher stiffness of graphite more than compensates for its smaller thickness due to the presence of the $+45^\circ$ and 90° layers.

Figure 11. Bending Results for Quasi-Isotropic Glass-Graphite Hybrid.

Conclusions

These results are intended to be representative of the behavior of hybrid laminates. To this end, a range of layups and material combinations was chosen that attempts to be fairly representative of the types of hybrid laminates that would be used. The trends discussed in this paper on the mechanical behavior of hybrid composites should provide useful qualitative information for designers. One salient point that arises from this study is that the behavior of hybrids, when the layer thicknesses of the materials are different, is quite complex. Also the elastic limits of hybrids can change drastically with the addition of a weaker material. This indicates that a complete strength analysis should be performed for each hybrid combination. Also, an extensive experimental program should be undertaken to verify these analytical results.

References

1. James M. Whitney, Isaac M. Daniels, and R. Byron Pipes, Experimental Mechanics of Fiber Reinforced Composite Materials, pp. 29-30, The Society for Experimental Stress Analysis, Brookfield Center, CT, 1982.
2. Joseph H. Faupel and Franklin E. Fisher, Engineering Design, pp. 307-315, John Wiley and Sons, New York, NY, 1981.
3. James N. Craddock and Dennis J. Champagne, "Comparison of Failure Criteria for Laminated Composite Materials," pp. in the Proceedings of the 23rd Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, Vol. , AIAA, New Orleans, LA, 1982.
4. S. W. Tsai and E. M. Wu, "A General Theory of Strength for Anisotropic Materials," Journal of Composite Materials, 5 (1) (1970), pp. 58-80.
5. S. W. Tsai and H. T. Hahn, Introduction to Composite Materials, pp. 19, 280-293, Technomic Publishing Co., Westport, CT, 1980.